

You want to know more about the *RethinkAction* project?

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Cross-sectoral planning decision-making platform to foster climate action

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About the *RethinkAction* project

RethinkAction is funded under the Horizon 2020-EU.3.5 Programme. The project brings together thirteen partners from nine countries, combining various fields of expertise such as social sciences, political science, land use based policy, environmental sciences, atmospheric sciences, ICT modelling, integrated assessment modelling, earth observation, climatology and communication.

During the four-year project period that started in October 2021, the *RethinkAction* team will develop a cross-sectoral decision-making platform tailored to the needs of different end-users. The platform will deliver clear and valuable information on climate change and increase awareness and attractiveness referring to land use based mitigation and adaptation solutions. The platform will be centered on land use as a key to sustain life and reach objectives in the context of climate change and will help

people to understand how individual changes in lifestyles as well as social behaviour can have an effect on land use in general. Moreover, it will allow users to access land use based adaptation and mitigation solutions linking local, European and global scales based on six representative case studies, covering the main regional differences related to climate change.

Within this approach *RethinkAction* aims to create awareness not only for political changes but also for individual behavioural changes. By developing solutions through participatory processes, the project will also promote active participation in climate action by decision-makers, stakeholders and citizens in Europe.

Our objectives

Engage

Explain

Transform